

Proposal Summary

The key, central objectives of this proposal are to

1. Develop showcase notebooks (i.e., Jupyter notebooks) around cloud-based NASA heliophysics and space weather datasets that engender a sense of excitement about open science (methods and outcomes) within the general science community by demonstrating powerful, interactive infrastructure for querying, visualization, investigating data governance and lineage, data lake navigation, and dataset discoverability.
2. Bootstrap a knowledge graph (KG) via coordinated human-expert modeling of taxonomies/ontologies and curation of high-quality metadata that describe said datasets.
3. Advance appreciation – among domain specialists and nonspecialists – of semantic knowledge representation approaches that lower data preparation efforts, enable deeper analyses based on enriching data context, and facilitate gathering a critical mass of domain awareness by interpreting and interlinking data from different sources.

Critical methods and techniques proposed to accomplish the stated objectives are:

1. Literate programming, as realized by the Jupyter project and, in particular, the Jupyter notebook format and the iPython kernel for interactive computing through a web-browser-based interface, as well as mature infrastructure for deploying environments for user sessions such as BinderHub for JupyterHub containers.
2. Resource-oriented (e.g., RESTful) HTTP APIs to query and subset cloud-based datasets for interactive exploration via e.g., Jupyter notebooks.
3. W3C Semantic Web standards for machine-actionable (FAIR) knowledge representation based on Web technologies. In particular, the Resource Description Framework (RDF) suite of standards for metadata querying (SPARQL), serialization (e.g., Turtle), exchange (e.g., HTTP media types), modeling and inferencing (e.g., RDF entailment), and validation (SHACL), as well as tooling (e.g., the Python RDFLib project) and infrastructure (e.g., open-source RDF graph databases).

The perceived significance of the proposed work to the objectives of the solicitation and to NASA interests and programs in general:

1. The bootstrapped knowledge graph will empower computer systems that in many aspects surpass the analytical capabilities that a typical human specialist has in their area of study. And unlike neural network models, the KG is human readable and explainable – one can use it as a reference data structure, correct it, govern it, publish it, etc. This is expected to allow more automation in scientific data management and to lower preparation efforts needed for AI projects across NASA that pertain to heliophysics and space weather.
2. By demonstrating the application of machine-actionable knowledge representation via showcase notebooks, the utility of semantic formalisms will be more accessible and concrete to both heliophysics / space weather specialists and to a broader community of nonspecialists that may interoperably interface with this field's open datasets.

1 Motivation

In recent decades, as storage media performance and sensor (platform) proliferation both vastly increased, we have seen an overabundance of data. Furthermore, many disciplines suffer from bespoke conceptualization of data, in either encoding (e.g., unique serialization or format) or how the data is structured and annotated – either of which are fully capable of siloing data. While the latter is beginning to converge (e.g., Heliophysics Events Knowledgebase (HEK) controlled vocabulary [14], the Space Physics Archive Search and Extract (SPASE) data model [18], and the Unified Astronomy Thesaurus (UAT) [12]), widespread adoption is still lacking, as well as large conceptual gaps in the existing vocabularies. This serves as a barrier to the discoverability of data, and an impedence to the velocity of science – when data cannot be found, it must be collected again; when data cannot be reused or integrated, it must be collected again.

Semantic technologies, as realized through knowledge graphs (KGs) and knowledge representation, are poised to accelerate science by emphasizing the notion of “smart data, not smart applications.” An effective knowledge representation which can be adapted in the face of an evolving field of science, and implemented through a KG, can create *smart* data by semantically harmonizing labels and conceptualization of data, and connecting together heterogeneous data sources.

Concretely, we propose to perform the following top-level tasks: **(a)** develop showcase, interactive Jupyter notebooks around discovering, querying, visualizing, and maintaining cloud-based NASA heliophysics and space weather datasets and **(b)** bootstrap a knowledge graph which provides mappings between well-known vocabularies and taxonomies for use with the produced notebooks in order to provide FAIR [30] datasets.

In doing so, we provide an opinionated approach to the creation and curation of data, emphasizing FAIR and Open Science Data practices. When new datasets are created through the use of our showcase notebooks, they will as an automated side-effect, produce appropriate metadata for the provenance and lineage of the datasets. Further, they can also provide annotations for the dataset (e.g., which features, events, or phenomena does the new dataset describe) which could be taken from a decentralized, community-driven schema. Finally, such metadata, produced for each new dataset, will allow a web of data, intrinsically forming the foundation for an open knowledge graph for heliophysics.

We describe our top-level goals, including our mission to advance the appreciation for semantic knowledge representation, in the next section (Section 2). In Section 3, we discuss the broader impacts of the work described in this proposal, and how it can complement downstream capacity building objectives. Section 4 presents in detail the exact technical approach that will be taken to produce the notebooks and bootstrapped KG. Finally, in Section 5, we provide the implementation plan and administrivia for meeting our goals.

2 Project Goals

The overarching goal of both the program and the proposed work is to advance the adoption of open science in heliophysics through practice, education, and engagement. The central goals of this proposal are organized into three work packages:

1. develop showcase Jupyter notebooks and supporting infrastructure and learning material to serve as a primary component in the *ScienceCore* for heliophysics (Section 4.1);
2. bootstrap a KG for open heliophysics, drawing on the power of persistent identifiers and W3C recommendations (Section 2.2); and
3. advance the appreciation of open science methods for heliophysics, primarily through community engagement (Section 2.3).

These work packages, and a top-level view of their dependencies, are shown in Figure 1. The first of our goals (i.e., the Jupyter notebooks) requires additional, supporting technical infrastructure that interfaces with existing NASA cloud-based heliophysics and space weather datasets, as well as the content and schema of the KG. The exact implementation details are included in Section 4.

2.1 ScienceCore for Heliophysics

The primary goal of this work package – and of this proposal writ large – is to contribute to the TOPS ScienceCore. We will do so by developing and linking showcase Jupyter notebooks which will provide an opinionated approach to interacting with cloud-based NASA heliophysics and space weather datasets. We have chosen the interactive Jupyter notebook approach as it (a) will most seamlessly integrate with semantic technologies, (b) aligns closely with existing data science workflows and technology stacks, and (c) allows for personal code sandboxing (i.e., learners can modify or add their own code for experiential learning).

These Jupyter notebooks will be used to demonstrate – and instruct – a wide range of competencies across domain science (i.e., heliophysics), broader data science literacy, and open science methods (e.g., semantic technologies). We wish to engender a sense of excitement about open science (both methods and outcomes) within the general science community – and in particular the heliophysics community – by demonstrating powerful, interactive infrastructure for querying, visualizing, investigating data governance and lineage, data lake navigation, and dataset discoverability.

Furthermore, the Jupyter notebooks will be developed according to a well-considered

Figure 1: The overarching technology and dependency stack between the project goals and deliverables.

and domain-informed curriculum. That is, self-contained notebooks (e.g., on the order of three cells) which demonstrate micro-topics in isolation – which we shall call *learning modules* – will be published to a public repository. Interactive versions will also be hosted for tutorials and preview access. By leveraging principles from literate programming [20], domain science can be interleaved with actionable code, resulting in a powerful teaching vehicle. Over time, we will grow the library of learner modules, and thus support more complex lesson plans. We intend to follow the five stages of skill acquisition from [10].

As the library of learning modules grows, we can create increasingly wider and interesting lesson plans by composing the modules. The KG will also play a role, here, by modeling the learning prerequisites (i.e., topic dependencies) which allows us to programmatically assemble chains of knowledge and learning materials.

Finally, this work package includes improving the robustness of the underlying technology stack that will support these notebooks, which has a traditional component (e.g., developing any missing RESTful APIs (REST – REpresentational State Transfer, API – application programmer interface) for in-demand datasets) and the semantic enrichment and connection component (which is described in Section 2.2). The exact implementation details are described in Section 4.1

2.2 A Bootstrapped Knowledge Graph for Heliophysics

The central mechanism this proposal endorses for promoting and enabling open heliophysics is through semantic technologies. This project goal concerns the development of an open heliophysics KG, constituting a web of (smart) heliophysics data, which as a result (a) integrates taxonomic resources; (b) connects people, artifacts, and phenomenology; and (c) models provenance and lineage of simulations, models, and datasets.

KGs are comprised of simple assertional statements that have the form *subject predicate object*, where each part is a persistent identifier. In this manner, one can encode nearly any assertion about the world. For example, one may say: `Alice hasFriend Bob`. But when looking through the lens of persistent identifiers (PIDs), one might prefix namespaces to these labels, as such: `ex:Alice ex:hasFriend ex:Bob`. In this example we use `ex` for “`https://example.com/`”. Namespaces disambiguate terms: this particular Alice is distinct from any other Alice in any other namespace.

A large portion of the integration capability that a KG offers is by making paramount and subsequently leveraging the power of persistent identifiers. For example, a study commissioned by the Australian Government suggests that \$24M AUD (\$16M USD) of *direct* financial cost could be recouped via saved effort in ensuring FAIR [30] access to data – especially the “F” and “A”, which stand for findable and accessible, respectively [4]. The cost and effort savings are likely to scale super-linearly with research output.

To this point, by using persistent identifiers for datasets, we are already halfway to a KG. The next step is to look at creating persistent identifiers – and associated semantics – of the relationships between nodes in a KG, such as `hasAuthor` which connects a research artifact to a person, or `generatedBy` which connects a dataset to a deployed sensor suite.

Thankfully, there is much work done on these sorts of predicates, taking the form of

W3C (World Wide Web Consortium) standards, such as the Semantic Sensor Network [7] and Provenance ontologies [26]. Furthermore, there are taxonomies, ontologies, and other controlled vocabularies that exist within heliophysics, space weather, and adjacent domains, such as the data models for HEK [14] and SPASE [18], as well as the UAT [12].

As part of the development process of an open heliophysics KG, we will necessarily need to fill gaps that these resources do not cover and provide mappings between them when the same phenomenon is described using a different label or slightly different definition across the taxonomic resources. Creating these mappings and combining them with the W3C recommendations and previous work (e.g., [28]) will result in a schema. As part of this work package, we will approach this in a principled manner, using the Modular Ontology Modeling methodology [27], which has been shown to produce reusable schema for KGs. From here, the KG can act as a convergence point between heliophysics phenomenology and other domains. For example, the KnowWhereGraph [16], the largest open geospatial KG, is largely concerned with hazards and natural events that occur *on* the Earth or in the atmosphere. Connecting these two resources could have an outsized effect on modeling causality of events pertaining to atmospheric sciences or the global communication systems.

Finally, this work package includes actually deploying the KG technology stack (e.g., on a triplestore, such as Apache Jena Fuseki [1]) and ensuring the stability of the SPARQL (SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language [13]) endpoint, which is used for querying the KG. The exact implementation details for this work package are provided in Section 4.2.

2.3 Advance Appreciation of Open Science Methods in Heliophysics

The third goal, which both serves and is informed by the previous goals, is to advance the appreciation – among domain specialists and nonspecialists – of semantic knowledge representation approaches that reduce data preparation efforts, enable deeper analyses based on enriching data context, and facilitate gathering a critical mass of domain awareness by interpreting and interlinking data from different sources, and overall drive the adoption of open science methods in heliophysics. We will accomplish this by **(a)** providing a well-polished and usable tool suite, **(b)** ensuring useful and usable outcomes at each stage, and **(c)** promoting and incorporating community involvement.

We can achieve for the first and second by leveraging the third. In particular, by identifying the traits that make a tool usable and tailoring its implementation, configuration, and output to be maximally useful to the users of the tool, we can easily advance appreciation of open science methods via *convenience* first. If the open science tool is the most usable, then open science as a byproduct of adoption is still open science. However, we do not have to stop there. By explicitly supporting semantic technologies, we can seamlessly enhance discoverability of data and encourage consensus and convergence of metadata.

In Section 4.3, we discuss in finer detail exactly how we will solicit usability and outcome concerns and needs from the community through usability sessions and community outreach.

3 Broader Impact

The proposed work is aligned with Strategic Goal 4 of NASA’s 2022 Strategic Plan: “Enhance Capabilities and Operations to Catalyze Current and Future Mission Success.” In particular, the proposed project goals will have a significant impact on NASA interests and programs in general.

The interactive Jupyter notebooks will provide a foundation for attracting talented and diverse workforce by serving as an accessible and usable demonstrator of open science, coupled with showcase visualizations and results in heliophysics and space weather, based on NASA cloud-based datasets.

The bootstrapped KG will empower computer systems that in many aspects surpass the analytical capabilities that a typical human specialist has in their area of study. And unlike neural network models, the KG is human readable and explainable – one can use it as a reference data structure, correct it, govern it, publish it, and so on. This is expected to allow more automation in scientific data management and to lower preparation efforts needed for AI projects across NASA that pertain to heliophysics and space weather.

And finally, by demonstrating the application of machine-actionable knowledge representation via showcase notebooks, the utility of semantic formalisms will be more accessible and concrete to both heliophysics and space weather specialists and to a broader community of nonspecialists that may interoperably interface with this field’s open datasets.

4 Technical Approach

The three project goals are develop showcase Jupyter notebooks, bootstrap an open heliophysics knowledge graph, and advance appreciation of open science methods. The first goals have deliverables associated with their work packages, and they have some dependencies, which can be seen in Figure 1, introduced above. In particular, the Jupyter notebooks (Section 4.1) rely on both some support infrastructure (the RESTful APIs) and the bootstrapped, open knowledge graph for heliophysics (Section 4.2). The support infrastructure will be worked on in parallel to the KG and semantic enrichment work. However, it is not an all-or-nothing process; as specific APIs and aspects of the KG are finalized, specific portions of the Jupyter notebooks will be developed.

The third work package (Advancing Appreciation) is not explicitly represented. Instead, as it wraps the usability and community engagement aspects of this proposal, it can be viewed as a periodic course correction for these two deliverables. It will give us a way to evaluate usability – by design – and will give us some notion of what should be prioritized, as indicated by the people that will use the software and tools. It will also allow to clarify any uncertainties and rectify sources of error, as they are encountered. This approach is described in more detail in Section 4.3.

4.1 Developing Showcase Jupyter Notebooks for Open Heliophysics

The deliverable for this work package is eponymous. These interactive, showcase Jupyter notebooks will be implemented using principles from literate programming. This is eas-

ily supported – and indeed encouraged, via the Jupyter notebook format and the iPython kernel for interactive computing through a web-browser-based interface. These notebooks can be hosted locally or on mature infrastructure for deploying environments for user sessions, such as BinderHub [3] for JupyterHub [17] containers.

These Jupyter notebooks are to serve a few different purposes: act as an educational entry point to the heliophysics and space weather concepts, demonstrate how to use heliophysics and space weather datasets, and encourage the use of open science methods, in particular through the use of semantic technologies.

For convenience in reading the rest of this section, we directly introduce several acronyms pertaining to persistent identifiers: **DOI**: Digital Object Identifier, **ORCID**: Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier, **ROR**: Research Organization Registry [25], **IGSN**: International Generic Sample Number [15], **RAID**: Research Activity Identification [24], and **PIDINST**: Persistent Identification of Scientific Instruments.

Curriculum Design We will follow a consistent design for the developed educational material. That is, the Jupyter notebooks developed for the ScienceCore for Heliophysics will have a standardized format with clearly described learning objectives. All actionable code will be well explained, in the style of literate programming. We will call a top-level Jupyter notebook a *lesson plan*, which demonstrates solutions, techniques, and technologies (e.g., software libraries) for open science tasks in heliophysics. A lesson plan will consist of several *modules*. Modules are atomic pieces of functionality, such as the execution of a specific query or mapping specific results to a visualization engine. We will initially develop six modules, with each directly concerning:

1. *Datasets* – refer to tabular or relational data resources, such as collections of sensor readings over a period of time. The persistent identifier for this category is the DOI, which may come from FigShare à la DataCite [9, 11], Zenodo [32], or a publisher.
2. *Agents* – are people (e.g., researchers) and their organizations (e.g., a university) . The persistent identifiers used are ORCID and ROR, respectively.
3. *(Material) Samples* – referring to physical samples that have been collected and are stored. The persistent identifiers used to reference these are IGSNs.
4. *Instruments* – are things that generate datasets, both physical instruments and their platforms or simulations and their models. There is no consensus for persistent identifiers for scientific instruments, yet we may point initially to PIDINST, a recommendation by the Research Data Alliance [22].
5. *Activities* – research activities, such as projects supported by grants. The persistent identifier for this category is the RAID.
6. *Reports/Analyses/Literature* – this module is concerned with identifying the relevant resources and access their metadata. The persistent identifier for this category of resources is the DOI, which may come from CrossRef [8], arXiv [2], or a publisher.

Each module will relate a query to an endpoint (e.g., SPARQL or RESTful API), demonstrate some manipulation (e.g., filtering, analysis, profiling, or linking), and visualization of the resultant data. These first modules will focus initially on displaying the power of persistent identifiers (PIDs), described above. These PIDs are easily related in a KG, quickly demonstrating the power and usefulness of semantic technologies. We fully intend to grow

the library of modules and support more complex lesson plans.

Supporting Infrastructure To actualize these Jupyter notebooks, we will develop supporting infrastructure. This will take the form as resource-oriented (e.g., RESTful) HTTP APIs to query and subset cloud-based datasets and the bootstrapped open knowledge graph for heliophysics.

Additionally, we will provide one or more Python libraries that will encapsulate the functionality of various open-source libraries for data retrieval and analysis specific to heliophysics and space weather (e.g., the `requests` for HTTP retrieval of open NASA datasets and `pandas` for manipulating panel data). Such packaging is crucial to reduce conceptual surface area for target users, making the material more accessible.

Finally, we will deploy the infrastructure for interactive notebook execution that will be needed in order to provide usability-testing participants with appropriately resourced environments (e.g., compute, storage, and networking capabilities), as well as to support the operational requirements of final deliverables (e.g., the notebooks to be hosted in the NASA TOPS GitHub repository), that may continue be used, evaluated, and tuned.

4.2 Bootstrapping an Open Heliophysics Knowledge Graph

In order to implement (bootstrap) an open heliophysics knowledge graph, we will rely on W3C Semantic Web standards for machine-actionable (FAIR [30]) knowledge representation based on Web technologies. In particular, the Resource Description Framework (RDF [31]) suite of standards for metadata querying (SPARQL [13]), serialization (e.g., Turtle [5]), exchange (e.g., HTTP media types), modeling and inferencing (e.g., RDF entailment), and validation (SHACL [19]), as well as tooling (e.g., the Python RDFLib project [23]) and infrastructure (e.g., open-source RDF graph databases). At a minimum, we will model metadata for heliophysics and space weather datasets and the connections between the people, simulations, and instruments that generate the datasets; and research activities, institutions, and funding agencies that support them.

Knowledge Graph Development will occur over three phases: **(a)** providing mappings between existing taxonomic resources (e.g., HEK, SPASE, and UAT); **(b)** collect all persistent identifiers found in Section 4.1 and create a shallow KG that connects them; and **(c)** extending the modular ontology for space weather research [28].

The first phase will be straight-forward, by soliciting feedback from the community, and building on previous workshops, we can encode connections between different taxonomic resources using `see_also` (a traditional thesaurus notation) and `sameAs` (from OWL) relations. Complex alignments can also be specified in OWL.

The second phase will largely be a traditional data aggregation task. However, after the identifiers are located and curated, we will need to integrate them. By treating each category of identifier as a *type* of data (or entity) we already quite close to a KG. What remains is to connect intuitive relations between them. For example, the provenance ontology [26] can be used to connect research artifacts (e.g., DOI) to authors (e.g., ORCID) to research activities (as in grants, identified with RAID PIDs).

The third, and final, phase, as it is extending prior work, will inherit the same development methodology: Modular Ontology Modeling [27], which is a pattern-based workflow for leveraging prior art and creating reusable schema for KGs. In [28], models have been developed for connected space weather events to the data that predicts them and can be significantly extended to support the open science mission. We will then revisit the output from the second phase and, where necessary, further enrich the semantics of the relations and add additional context information to each entity.

KG Infrastructure Development and Deployment will be required to carry out this effort. In particular, we will deploy and host a triplestore (currently foreseen to be Apache Jena Fuseki [1], an open-source triplestore) that will provide access to the KG via a SPARQL endpoint. The interactive, showcase Jupyter notebooks will provide examples on how to connect to the triplestore, execute queries against it, and interpret the results. Furthermore, it will demonstrate idioms from common Python libraries for manipulating RDF data (e.g., RDFlib).

4.3 Advancing Appreciation of Open Science Methods

The primary mechanism by which we intend to advance appreciation of open science methods in heliophysics is through the principled involvement of community feedback on the usability, performance, and development of our tools (i.e., the Jupyter notebooks). There are, in turn, two ways that we intend to accomplish this. First, we intend to hold consistent usability sessions that involve (transparently) selected domain experts. Then, we outline a broad framework for initiating and maintaining community engagement across several media.

Usability Sessions As mentioned already several times, we will develop the Jupyter notebooks and supporting tool suite (e.g., endpoints and APIs) in a principled, user-centric manner. In particular, we choose to follow the methodology as outlined in [21] for executing usability studies. The PI has significant previous experience in executing this methodology in interdisciplinary applications. The methodology “Rocket Surgery Made Easy” is a low time-commitment, high impact methodology which is well-suited for small teams that are constrained by budget, and it is particularly amenable to both internal and community-driven initiatives. Perhaps most importantly, it is resilient to prototyping, as it focuses on the user interaction and experience, more so than the specific domain minutiae.

We anticipate to hold ten usability sessions per year, following the outlined methodology, which will occur approximately monthly (skipping a month in Q4 and Q1 for the holidays).

A usability (testing) session will be constructed as follows. The PI will lead the session, as according to the methodology. An external consultant which shall have expertise in knowledge representation and semantic technologies will be present. These two shall represent the tool (e.g., Jupyter notebooks) at hand. Participants will be selected from close domain collaborators from heliophysics. While this is a targeted invitation, we want to include diverse opinion. In each usability session, the PI will attempt to rotate domain

Figure 2: The project schedule organized into four segments, each capped by a Milestone.

expert participants in such a way that breadth of opinion is maximized, but momentum and vision from previous sessions is maintained. One approach may be to hold one participant in common, but not for longer than two sessions consecutively.

We initially intend to support three domain experts during each session. The nature of this support is outlined in the Budget Narrative. As we converge on real support costs, the extent and nature of support may increase. In the end, we will produce a usable set of interactive, showcase Jupyter notebooks for interacting with, querying, visualizing, navigating, and discovering cloud-based NASA heliophysics and space weather datasets.

Community Engagement In order to drive wider community engagement, we will focus on broadening participation outside of heliophysics domain experts. We will assume, however, that participants will have basic data science literacy (e.g., those who have already completed *OpenCore* modules or their equivalent, or who have equivalent experience) and are interested in deepening specific domain knowledge.

To accomplish this, we will support a number of synchronous and asynchronous methods of participation. For the former, we will conduct live webinars to demonstrate and facilitate real-time engagement and feedback with developed material, e.g. Carpentries-style [6] lessons (the PI is a certified Carpentries instructor and has co-lead workshops at national laboratories, academic institutes, and companies). For the latter, we will provide a digital space (e.g., Zulip [33], an open-source platform alternative to e.g. Slack [29]) to: **(a)** share recordings and transcriptions of the webinars; **(b)** host forum-style, moderated Question and Answer threads, which shall produce curated conversation records; and **(c)** support broader semi-synchronous community discussions. Finally, all training material (e.g., text within Jupyter notebooks) and transcriptions will be translated into at least one other language (i.e., Spanish) using professional services where possible. As a result, we will have constructed a framework for initiating and maintaining community engagement.

5 Implementation Plan

Project Schedule as shown in Figure 2, identifies when we have reached our key milestones for accomplishments and dependencies between tasks. The Usability Sessions will occur every month (minus two). This allows us to organize the project into four segments

of five-month length. Orange boxes reference work done for developing the showcase, interactive Jupyter notebooks (Sections 2.1 and 4.1). Blue boxes reference work done for bootstrapping the open knowledge graph for heliophysics (Sections 2.2 and 2.2). Each milestone month will involve solicitation of expert and community feedback, and a release of all material, including drafts.

- **Milestone 1:** *Goal 1:* all datasets that require a RESTful API or will be included in the open KG have been identified; API development has begun for several datasets; a draft of the curriculum design has been completed; and mock-ups for the Jupyter notebooks have been produced and tested. *Goal 2:* mappings between different taxonomic resources have been identified and encoded and a draft of the shallow KG for connecting PIDs has been completed.
- **Milestone 2:** *Goal 1:* all API development has been completed; curriculum design is under way; and at least one Jupyter Notebook (JN) has been completed. *Goal 2:* the shallow KG for connecting PIDs has been completed and a draft for extending prior KG work in space weather has been completed.
- **Milestone 3:** *Goal 1:* the curriculum design has been finalized and Jupyter notebook development continues apace. *Goal 2:* the extended KG has been completed.
- **Milestone 4:** *Goal 1* all Jupyter notebooks have been completed. *Goal 2:* each previous work item has been integrated into the final KG.

Management Structure This is a single-PI proposal. The PI will, of course, be responsible for the overall management and tracking of deliverables. As this proposal expects significant contribution from external consultants, the PI will directly manage the distribution of work items for any consultants and regularly check quality of deliverables and progress on milestones.

Collaborations There is expected to be significant collaboration with the Center for HelioAnalytics, as members will be invited to attend the usability design sessions as described in Section 2.3 and 4.3.

Proposed Use of Consultants This proposal expects the use of consultants. Each consultant shall provide relevant domain expertise and leverage their network to bootstrap community involvement and shall provide expertise regarding semantic technologies for creating, evolving, and maintaining the knowledge graph and associated technology stack.

Expected Contributions As this is a single PI-proposal, the PI will attend and be responsible for every task and subtask listed in Figure 2. The external consultant will be primarily used to inform the Knowledge Graph Development tasks, but will also contribute overall insight to the open science aspects of every task in the proposal.

Open-Source Science Development Plan

Types of data and metadata standards to be used in the course of the project This project will be dedicated to the use of existing openly licensed metadata standards, in particular the W3C recommendations RDF, OWL, SPARQL, and SHACL. The Jupyter notebooks will of course utilize the open-source Jupyter ecosystem, and will leverage only openly licensed Python libraries (e.g., rdflib).

Resources and facilities to store and preserve data Publications, presentations, and educational material will be stored and made available to the general public via a dedicated project website which will be hosted by the PI. All educational material, including seminar presentations, will be freely available to professionals, students, and other educators via the project website. During the project duration, interactive versions will be hosted, and will for as long as support lasts. Provision of the base code and artifacts will always be available through data and software preservation sites, e.g., GitHub.

Policies for data access and sharing Any open data created will be registered at open data repositories such as the Registry of Research Data Repositories (re3data.org), Figshare (figshare.com), or Zenodo (zenodo.org). Only a web browser will be needed to access the data files, which will be stored in open-source formats.

Policies for provision and data re-use Any published journal articles and conference papers will transfer copyright to the journal or conference. No embargo restrictions for publications or curated data are anticipated. The deliverables will not involve any proprietary, confidential, or privacy sensitive data. Any software produced will be made available for use free of cost, as open-source software under the Apache-2.0 license. All ontologies and test data originally produced as part of the project, will be made available for use free of cost, under the CC0 license. The software developed in the project will be made available through a public git repository, e.g. on GitHub. Availability and development of the software will therefore persist beyond the conclusion of the project.

Plans for data archiving and preservation of access to them after the award ends At the conclusion of the project, the PI will continue to host and maintain project-related Web sites and also archive any data approved for release that may be of general interest to the research community in appropriate institutional repositories.

The roles and responsibilities of parties, and contingencies, for data management The PI will be responsible for the management of data. This includes publishing of code updates to a public git repository, self-archiving of publications and presentations in institutional repositories, and responsible archiving of data. Data registration is included in the process of archiving this data. The PI will ensure that data and code are maintained and available beyond the conclusion of the project.

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